

INTERMEDIATE RESULTS OF CAV IMPACT DIAGRAM DEVELOPMENT

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Introduction

This document contains information on the intermediate results of the impact diagram development process described in the paper “Impact assessment methodology for connected and automated vehicles” by Cleij et al.. First the intermediate results for the diagram set up are described. This includes the initial list of impacts based on an explorative literature review and the initial impact diagrams that follow from this review in combination with project member inputs. Second, the intermediate results of the diagram elaboration phase are provided. This includes three iterations of analysing and updating the impact diagrams as well as analysing and updating the impacts when grouped along the dimensions “vehicle user”, “transportation operations” and “society”. The third iteration resulted in the final impact diagrams from which the final list of impacts was extracted.

Throughout the elaboration phase additional literature was found. An overview of the most relevant literature from both the set up and elaboration phases can be found in LEVITATE project deliverable D3.1.

Impact Diagram Set Up

Impact list based on explorative literature review

The following list of potential impacts of connected and automated transport systems was derived from the initial explorative literature review described in the underlying data document “Cleijetal2021_ExplorativeLiteratureOverview.pdf”:

- Safety
- Road capacity
- Infrastructure wear
- Travel time
- Geographic accessibility
- Land use
- Vehicle kilometres of travel
- Optimisation of route choice
- Vehicle ownership cost
- Vehicle operating costs
- Use and valuation of travel time
- Travel comfort
- Vehicle ownership rates
- Use of shared mobility services
- Shifts in market shares of transport modes
- Changes in commuting distances
- Energy efficiency of transport
- Vehicle emissions
- Individual accessibility to transport

Initial impact diagrams

From the explorative literature review and project member inputs a first impact diagram was developed. The diagram consists of primary impacts and secondary (feedback) impact which are visualized in two different diagrams in Figure 1 and Figure 2, respectively.

Figure 1: Initial impact diagram with primary impacts, based on impacts described in papers from explorative literature review and input from project members

Impact Diagram Elaboration

The first diagram was further developed in the “diagram elaboration” step of the process. In this section three iterations of this process are shown. The process consists of 1) analysing the existing diagrams and 2) regrouping the impacts along common dimensions, with the goal of improving the diagrams.

First iteration

Analyzing the initial diagram set up and regrouping the impacts during the first iteration led to several changes to the diagram, mainly involving additional interrelations. The changes after the first iteration are highlighted using thick red contours in Figure 3 and Figure 4, while Figure 5 shows the grouping of the corresponding impacts along the dimensions “vehicle users”, “transportation operations” and “society”.

Ripples

Figure 3: Impact diagram with primary impacts after first iteration

Feedback

Figure 4: Impact diagram with secondary impacts after first iteration

Figure 5: Grouping of impacts, based on the first iteration impact diagrams using the main groups vehicle users, transport operations and society

Second iteration

During a second iteration the impact diagram was revised more rigorously, such that the impacts could logically be structured under direct, systematic and wider impacts as shown in Figure 6 and Figure 7. In Figure 8 the corresponding impacts are again grouped along the previously mentioned dimensions and changed with Figure 5 are highlighted with thick red contours.

Figure 6: Impact diagram with primary impacts after second iteration

Secondary impacts (behavioural adaptation)

Figure 7: Impact diagram with secondary impacts after second iteration

Figure 8: Grouping of impacts, based on the second iteration impact diagrams using the main groups vehicle users, transport operations and society

Third iteration

After a third and final iteration the final diagrams were obtained as shown in Figure 9 and Figure 10. Here the changes compared to the diagrams from the second iteration are highlighted with a cyan thick contour when added and a red thick contour when removed. As no impacts were added or removed the grouping diagram is the same in the second and third iteration.

Primary impacts

Figure 9: Final impact diagram with primary impacts

Secondary impacts (behavioural adaptation)

Figure 10: Final impact diagram with secondary impacts

Figure 11: Grouping of impacts, based on the final impact diagrams using the main groups vehicle users, transport operations and society

Final list of impacts

From the diagrams of the last iteration a final list of impacts was extracted. The impacts and a brief description are shown in Table 1.

Impact	Description of impact
Direct impacts	
Travel time	Duration of a trip between a given origin and a given destination
Travel comfort	Subjective rating of the level of comfort on a given trip
Value of travel time	Willingness to pay for reduced travel time
Vehicle operating cost	Direct outlays for operating a vehicle per kilometre of travel
Vehicle ownership cost	The cost of buying and keeping a vehicle
Access to travel	The opportunity of taking a trip whenever and wherever wanted
Route choice (individual)	Technology to support the best choice of route on a given trip
Systemic impacts	
Amount of travel	Vehicle kilometres or person kilometres of travel per year in an area
Road capacity	The maximum number of vehicles that can pass a section of road per unit of time
Congestion	Delays to traffic as a result of high traffic volume
Infrastructure wear	The rate per unit of time at which a road is worn down
Infrastructure design	Equipping roads with technology for vehicle-to-infrastructure communication
Modal split of travel	The distribution of trips between modes of transport
Optimisation of route choice	Direction of vehicles to routes that minimise overall generalised cost of travel for traffic as a total
Vehicle ownership rate	Percent of households owning 0, 1, 2 etc vehicles
Shared mobility rate	Percent of trips made sharing a vehicle with others
Vehicle utilisation rate	Share of time a vehicle is in motion (not parked); cabin factor (share of seats in use)
Parking space	Size of areas designated for parking
Traffic data availability	The availability of detailed trip data for transport planning
Market penetration rate	Percentage of CAVs in the relevant market
Wider impacts	
Trust in technology	Share of population indicating high trust in automation technology
Road safety	The number and severity of accidents
Propulsion energy	Source of energy used to move vehicles (fossil fuel or electric)
Energy efficiency	Rate at which propulsion energy is converted to movement; rate of loss due to conversion of energy to heat or noise rather than movement
Vehicle emissions	Emissions in micrograms per kilometre per vehicle (by chemical)
Air pollution	Concentration of pollutants per cubic metre of air
Noise pollution	Number of individuals exposed to noise above a certain threshold
Public health	Incidence of morbidity and mortality; subjectively rated health state
Employment	Changes in number of people employed in given occupations
Geographic accessibility	Time used to reach a given destination from different origins
Inequality in transport	Statistics indicating skewness in the distribution of travel behaviour between groups according to social status
Commuting distances	Length of trips to and from work
Land use	Density of land use for given purposes (residential, industrial, etc.)
Public finances	Income and expenses of the public sector

Table 1: Final list of impacts

Relevant literature

Throughout the diagram development process additional literature was found. An overview of the literature most relevant for the diagram development was described in Chapter 2 of the LEVITATE project deliverable D3.1 and can be found in the underlying data document

“Cleijetal2021_OverviewOfMostRelevantLiterature.pdf”